

Parking Lots

A parking lot company provides parking services. Today, the company owns various parking lots throughout the country. The company is interested in automating the parking lots. For this purpose, a request has been made to develop an information system that supports the relevant processes. For each parking lot, the system will store a unique number, name, address, and city. An administrator will be responsible for entering these details into the system.

Large touch screens will be installed at the entrance gate and the conveyor belt stations for operation. The touch screen at the entrance gate will be used to receive customers' requests (for example, payments). Alternatively, customers can communicate with the system via a mobile application. The system will display (on the touch screen or the application) the number of available parking spaces in the parking lot (0 if the parking lot is full). The entrance or exit of a vehicle will update the displayed number in real-time. To this end, a gate sensor (GS) will be installed at the entrance to a parking lot, identifying the arrival and departure of vehicles.

When a vehicle approaches the gate sensor, the system will search for the vehicle number in the database. If found, the vehicle data will be displayed. If not found, a camera installed at the entrance will take a photo of the vehicle, and the system will display the vehicle number and photo. The driver will be requested to use the touchscreen to enter: first name, last name, and mobile phone, which will be stored in the system alongside the vehicle details. If the customer exists, the vehicle will be added to their vehicle list. Each vehicle will be associated with one customer only.

After displaying the vehicle details, the customer will click "confirm entry." The system will display a parking ticket with a unique barcode, date, time, and vehicle number. The gate will open and the vehicle will be able to enter. Customers with the app can view details there.

The customer will drive to the conveyor area, park on a vacant conveyor, leave the vehicle in neutral, take the key, and lock the vehicle. The conveyor sensor (CS) will scan the vehicle number and display the parking details on the conveyor screen. The customer will confirm vehicle handover. The system will run an optimization algorithm to assign the nearest vacant space to the conveyor location. The system will save this data and display it, including the unique barcode and the exact location (floor number and space number in the floor). An SMS message with parking details will be sent to the customer's phone. This data is also available in the application. The conveyor will move the vehicle to the designated space.

For getting the vehicle back, the customer will approach a computer station (or alternatively use the application), enter the parking number, and click "end parking." Upon requesting to end parking, the conveyor transfers the vehicle to the parking lot gate. The gate sensor will identify the vehicle, and the customer will be requested to pay with a credit card reader, which is installed at the exit point. The system will calculate the payment amount according to a fixed hourly price list (or parts thereof). Each parking lot will have a separate price list, which may change from time to time. The system will maintain price history for each parking lot, including the update date, price for the first hour (or part of it), price for each additional hour (or part of it), and price for a full day. The system will transmit the payment request to the credit card company for approval. Once the card is approved, the gate will open, a printed receipt will be issued, and the vehicle will be allowed to exit. The receipt will also be available in the mobile application. For regulatory compliance, all parking data and payments will be saved for one year. Each parking record will include the end time and receipt details: receipt number, confirmation number (from the credit company), and receipt date. Credit card details are not stored.

The company is willing to manage a customer club to improve customer service. Customers can join through the application or through the touchscreen station at the entrance to the parking lot, and provide additional details: ID number, email, and birth date. At the end of each month, the marketing manager

sends email messages to the club members with a list of coupons for the coming month. The marketing manager will define these discount coupons in the system, and they will be viewable in the application for club members. For each coupon, the system will store a coupon number, description, and validity period (from and to dates). Examples of coupons include: "50% discount", "10% off parking", "15 NIS discount". Before paying for parking, the customer can redeem a coupon. When a coupon is redeemed, the system will store the redemption date. The marketing manager can generate the coupon redemption report for a selected period. To do so, the manager will enter the desired date range. The report will include the following details: for each coupon defined during the selected period, the coupon name will be displayed. In addition, for each coupon, a list of customers who redeemed it will be shown. For each customer, their club membership details and the date of redemption will be included.

The administrator and the marketing manager access the system from the office desktop computer where the system is installed.